

DOWNY OAK: RENDERING ECOPHYSIOLOGICAL PROCESSES IN PLANTS AUDIBLE

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ABSTRACT

In our research project *trees: Rendering Ecophysiological Processes Audible*, we are working on the acoustic recording, analysis and representation of ecophysiological processes in plants and studying the acoustic and aesthetic requirements for making them perceptible. Measurements of acoustic emissions in plants are only interpretable in relation to climatic and physiological dynamics such as microclimatic conditions, sap flow and changes in trunk radius and water potential within the plants—all measurement data that is not auditory per se. Therefore, our work involves analysing the acoustic emissions mathematically, on one hand, and sonifying ecophysiological data on the other. How can phenomena that are beyond our normal perception be made directly observable, creating new experiences and opening a new window on the processes of nature? The sound installation *trees: Downy Oak*, exhibited at swissnex in San Francisco in summer 2012, is a first approach to a spatial audio sonification and research system. Our experiments show that immediate and intuitive access to measurement data through sounds and their spatial positioning is very promising in terms of new forms of data display as well as generative art works.

INTRODUCTION

The link between trees and various climatic processes is usually not immediately apparent. Plants, in general, do not live merely on moisture from rain, sunlight (which drives gas exchange) and nutrients from the soil: they also absorb carbon dioxide from the air and produce the oxygen that we breathe, maintaining our climate and biosphere. Hence the interest in cooperation between a biologist and an artist to conduct research and measurements to study the complex relationship between tree physiology and the climate on one hand and to explore the possibilities of acoustic and artistic representations of ecophysiological processes in trees on the other. Rendering audible the way in which water transport or trunk diameter, for example, are influenced by sunlight, humidity and wind allows us to identify and better understand plants' responses to climatic processes.

1.1 “Phytoacoustics”

Plant physiologists have known that plants emit sounds for several decades now. Many of these sounds are of transpiratory/hydraulic origin and are therefore related to the circulation of water and air within the plant as part of the transpiration process. The frequencies of these acoustic emissions lie mostly in the ultrasonic range, depending on the species-specific characteristics of the plant tissues.

Fig. 1: An acoustic sensor (under the yellow tape) and a sap flow sensor (covered by reflective insulation material) mounted on a branch of a Scots pine in the Swiss Alps in summer 2012.

Some of the acoustic emissions are indications of embolism in the water transport system, which occurs when a plant is subjected to drought stress and desiccation. The excessive water tension in the water-conducting system leads to the rupture of the water columns in the plant vessels. Many studies have analysed these acoustic emissions in quantitative terms (number of emissions over time) but few have focused on the signal properties (frequencies, waveforms and amplitudes) so far or on the spatial distribution within the plant.

Each plant species—in fact each plant individual—has its own acoustic signature, related to its structure and to the local climatic conditions. Investigating the acoustic emissions of a tree in response to dynamically changing climatic conditions might reveal biological or physical properties that place them in a broader ecophysiological context and enable us to explain processes that are not yet fully understood.

Various artistic projects have subjected plant sounds to an artistic investigation with a view to revealing a world that is normally inaudible. These include Justin Bennett's *Hoor de Boomen*, Alex Metcalf's *Tree Listening* and Christa Sommerer and Laurent Mignonneau's *Data Tree* to name just a few. Our project (which is situated between the domains of artistic research and natural science) examines the aesthetic means of illustrating phenomena in nature but also aims to generate new knowledge through exploration using artistic and sound technology tools, systems and practices.

Fig. 2: Acoustic emissions of a sunflower fully exposed to sunlight. The high frequency signals represent the supposed cavitation pulses.

1.2 Sonification of ecophysiological data

The representation of data using sound (among other means) can help to exploit the effectiveness of our sense of hearing in grasping complex contexts both through immediate orientation in space and intuitive classification of sound characteristics. Sonification offers a deep and broad insight into multidimensional data, enabling us to recognize patterns and providing an aesthetic and emotional experience of scientific discoveries.

Gathering ecophysiological data (i.e. conducting measurements of the local climatic and environmental conditions and of the physiological processes within a plant in response to these) has become an important method in research on climate change and vegetation dynamics. It helps to determine physiological thresholds of plants in terms of increasing temperature and consequently drought stress. A downy oak in the central Alps, for example, is able to withstand the current climatic conditions of the air and soil whereas a Scots pine is pushed beyond its physiological limits despite the fact that both tree species have coexisted there for thousands of years. Consequently, shifts in the abundance of tree species are observed, and the ecophysiological knowledge acquired explains the underlying processes.

In our project, we began by combining field recordings of meteorological phenomena, recordings of acoustic emissions in trees and acoustic representations (sonifications) of ecophysiological data in a single auditory experience and making their correlation acoustically and aesthetically experienceable and explorable. We conducted a number of sonification experiments based on ecophysiological data collected by Roman Zweifel (WSL) and Fabienne Zeugin of the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) on an ongoing basis on a downy oak (*Quercus pubescens*) at Salgesch in the Swiss mountains in 2003 and 2004. Zweifel and Zeugin measured relative air humidity, sap flow, stem radius changes and ultrasonic acoustic emissions (UAE) throughout an entire tree growth cycle and recorded the data at ten-minute intervals throughout the day and night.

Fig. 3: Typical diurnal courses of acoustic emissions (UAE; cycles) in relation to branch sap flow rate (line) of a downy oak (*Quercus pubescens*) at Salgesch from 24 to 25 June 2004.

As the data relating to the ecophysiological processes was multidimensional, an analytical system was needed that focused on the key factors and the interrelations between these and rendered them intuitively perceptible. In terms of sound technology, the use of a spatial audio system immediately suggested itself for the sonification experiments as a means of spatially separating, distributing and conveying sounds and sound sequences. We were aware of comparable systems being developed at the Institute for Electronic Music and Acoustics (IEM) in Graz (Data Listening Space) 0 and at the ZKM in Karlsruhe (Cube) 0.

2. DOWNY OAK: A PROTOTYPE OF A SPATIAL AUDIO SONIFICATION SYSTEM

The sound installation *trees: Downy Oak*, exhibited at swissnex in San Francisco in summer 2012, is a preliminary approach to our intended research system and a work of art at the same time. It is the prototype of a spatial audio matrix that we will use during our future sonification experiments.

2.1 The audio system

The system (the *trees: Downy Oak* installation) consists of a grid of 36 self-built omni-directional speakers. It is designed as a cube matrix with an additional layer of speakers on top. Visitors can walk around the installation freely and explore it.

The Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology has conducted research and development in Ambisonics-based surround technology since its foundation in 2005. One of the limitations concerning placement and moving of virtual audio sources in an Ambisonics sound field is that the perceived positions of the sources remain outside the speaker system. The virtual sound sources are projected onto the surface of a virtual (usually) half sphere, which is mapped on and distributed through a multichannel speaker system. The perceptual situation is comparable to listening to what is going on outside through an open window: An Ambisonics system is not able to project virtual sound sources onto a spot within the system's boundaries.

Fig. 5: The sound installation *trees: Downy Oak* at swissnex in San Francisco in summer 2012.

Our idea consisted in creating a three-dimensional speaker array in which virtual sound sources could be moved and placed *within* a defined space, allowing listeners to walk around inside the system. The speaker matrix that we developed for the *trees: Downy Oak* installation is currently a hybrid sound system: The Ambisonics sound field is mapped onto the outer surface of the cube matrix. The vertical speaker line in the middle is driven discretely. Our goal with newer versions of the system is to implement cross-fading algorithms between the speakers of the matrix so as to allow free placement and movement of virtual sound sources within the cube.

2.2 Downy Oak: Data sonification

The sonification system is based on a combination of different sonification techniques, i.e. playback of audifications of original acoustic emission recordings (by transposing them into the audible domain) and parameter mapping sonification, whereby the sound parameters of a sample player (amplitude, pitch and filters) and the sound distribution system (spatial position or movements of virtual sound sources) are controlled by the data flow.

The different sonification modules are implemented in a set of Max Patches, which replays the measurement data of a downy oak throughout an entire growth cycle (April-October 2004). For an adequate (temporal) experience of the key processes, the speed of the running

system is increased up to 36 times the normal speed to take into account the ten-minute measuring intervals. Environmental data is mapped onto the outside of the cube, while tree data is played back on the vertical speaker line in the middle of the array.

A larger number of ecophysiological and meteorological phenomena do not manifest themselves acoustically, and it was a challenging task to generate metaphorical sounds to portray a single phenomenon, such as sunlight or air humidity effectively. The following table shows the phenomena (i.e. the data), the kind of sounds that represent them and the individual playback parameters, controlled by the data flow and mapping:

Data	Sound characteristics	Playback parameters
Sun position [azimuth, altitude]; sunlight [W/m^2]	String-like, synthetic sound	Spatial position; amplitude
Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	-	Main volume
Rel. air humidity [%]	Water-like, synthetic sound	Pitch, amplitude
Rain [mm]	Field rec.: rain	Amplitude, spatial position
Wind [m/sec., azimuth]	Field rec.: wind	Amplitude, spatial position
Soil water potential [kPa]	Field rec.: seeping water	Amplitude
Tree trunk diameter [μm]	-	High pass filter, applied on sap flow sound
Tree sap flow [$\text{g H}_2\text{O}/\text{h}$]	Floating water, transposed up and filtered	Amplitude
Tree ultrasonic acoustic emissions/cavitation pulses [dB]	Field rec.: ultrasonic acoustic emissions, transposed down	Amplitude

3. PRELIMINARY CONCLUSIONS

For us as well as for visitors, it was and still is a fascinating experience to spend time in the system, listening to the interplay of sounds and the related phenomena throughout an entire growth period, which lasts about 40 minutes. Besides the diurnal course of the tree's response to sunlight, there are many other recognizable patterns: As it gets drier in the summer, the cavitation events become longer, sometimes lasting deep into the night; the stressed plant needs more time to refill with water from the soil. In addition, the number of cavitation sounds is greater when a plant is well drained and exposed to full sunlight than in very dry periods.

Immediate and intuitive access to measurement data through sound and its spatial positioning is very promising as it offers new forms of data display and observation of processes in nature as well as generative art works. The representation and sonification of our tree data needs to become more complex: At present, there are just three parameters mapped onto a single vertical

line of the audio matrix: sap flow, cavitation and trunk diameter, measured at the stem of the tree. We would like to include more information about the spatial distribution of the acoustic emissions and the related physiological measurements within a whole plant, including the crown, the root and some branches at various locations on the tree.

Our intention in presenting a first prototype of the sonification system at a public exhibition was to determine whether or not our initial experiments would be comprehensible to a broader audience, i.e. whether or not the ecophysiological phenomena and their interrelations could be identified through the chosen sounds and the design of our experiential space. Visitors had no major problems identifying most of the field recordings, but it became evident that the different sounds and their meanings needed to be explained. We set up a computer with a blog explaining the sounds and corresponding phenomena and their interplay. In addition, visitors were encouraged to leave comments about their experience of the installation. We also realized that additional elements were needed within the installation, particularly information about the time of day and season. We solved that problem on site by projecting the date and time of the sonified measurements onto the floor next to the installation.

Regarding the further development of our system, we are currently examining different forms of visual information as supportive elements. We think it would be helpful to have video information about the time of day, the course of the sun, the weather conditions etc. Daniel Bisig and Jan Schacher have been working on immersive audio-visual environments since 2010. In their recent research project *Immersive Lab* at the ICST, they are experimenting with an audio-visual setup that offers haptic interaction with generative art pieces. Alongside further development of our 3D speaker-matrix, we intend to integrate our sonification processes with the *Immersive Lab* installation adding panoramic/hemispheric video recordings.

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